

Overall study design

Title of the study	Mouse brain study		
Document creation date	03/27/2024	Corresponding Email	dominik.kopczynski@univie.ac.at
Principle investigator	Dominik Kopczynski	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Institution	University of Vienna	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	1-phase system	1-phase system	Acetonitrile
pH adjustment	None	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

MS type	Q	MS Level	MS1
MS vendor	Agilent	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	Low resolution
Ion source	ESI	Resolution in Da at MS1	0
Direct type	Syringe	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	No
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	No
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	Nope
Summary data	Quantification data, Identification data		

Sample Descriptions

HATA 054 / Human / Urine

Provided information	Time to freeze (min)	Additives	lipase Inhibitors
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	Yes
Time to freeze (min)	40.0	Type of preservation method	Aluminum foil
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	Yes
Storage temperature	Room temperature		

MM201 / Mouse / Plasma

Provided information	Storage time (month)	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	Yes
Storage temperature	Room temperature	Type of preservation method	Deep freezer
Storage time (month)	3	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) TG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Additional dimension/techniques	IMS
Identification level	Molecular species level	CCS verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isobaric/isomeric interference
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	Yes
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

1) TG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

2) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CL	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Additional dimension/techniques	IMS
Identification level	Molecular species level	CCS verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	For separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-2H]2-	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	Yes
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

2) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

3) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Background check at MS1	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Background check at MS2	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Check isomer overlap	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name	all cats are beautiful and clever		
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-

3) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Type I isotope correction	Yes
MS Level for quantification	MS1, MS2	Limit of quantification	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Normalization to reference	No
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE	PE		
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Rock	Me	Amadeus	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-

4) PA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Background check at MS1	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Background check at MS2	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Check isomer overlap	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
all			
cats			
are			
beautiful			
and			
clever			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-

4) PA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE	PE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

5) DMPE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DMPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Polarity mode	Negative	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	No		

5) DMPE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
DMPE	DMPE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

6) PA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Polarity mode	Negative	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	No		

6) PA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE	PE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

7) DMPE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DMPE	Background check at MS1	No														
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Background check at MS2	No														
Identification level	Molecular species level	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No														
Polarity mode	Negative	Check isomer overlap	No														
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-														
Fragments for identification	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer															
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Fragment name</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>all</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>cats</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>are</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>beautiful</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>and</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>clever</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				Fragment name		all		cats		are		beautiful		and		clever	
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Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Smoothing														
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes														
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A														
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-														

7) DMPE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No				
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No				
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1	Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Internal standard</td> <td>Endogenous subclass</td> </tr> <tr> <td>DMPE</td> <td>DMPE</td> </tr> </table>				Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	DMPE	DMPE
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass						
DMPE	DMPE						
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC				
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-				
Type I isotope correction	Yes						

8) FAA[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FAA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No				
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	No				
Identification level	Species level	Additional dimension/techniques	-				
Polarity mode	Positive	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer				
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H]+	Data manipulation	-				
Fragments for identification	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Fragment name</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ada</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				Fragment name		Ada	
Fragment name							
Ada							
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A				
MS2 verified by standard	No	Further identification remarks	-				
Background check at MS2	No						

8) FAA[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-